

Air Force Opto-Electronic Focus for C³I

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Abstract - This paper will focus on Air Force Rome Laboratory optoelectronic systems, devices, and components currently being developed to support Photonic Signal Processing and Optical Memory for Air Force Command, Control, Communications and Intelligence (C³I) Applications. The specific thrusts in opto-electronic integrated circuits, interconnects, networks, & memory, leading to near real time signal processing capability for surveillance, communications, intelligence, avionics, and compact processors will be described.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Rome Laboratory is the lead Air Force Laboratory for C³I technology. In order to define the Rome Laboratory's role in Command and Control (C²) research and development, it is first necessary to discuss a C² topology and a common set of definitions. There is a vast body of literature on the subject of "C²", including reports, studies, and white papers produced both within and outside the defense establishment.[6] A review of the key literature developed at the DoD and Service levels, provides a topology or framework in which to describe a set of common attributes for C². The attributes also define where research and development must be pursued.

The following three themes were found to be constantly repeated, albeit by different names:

1. Global Awareness
2. Dynamic Planning and Execution
3. Seamless Communications/Connectivity

Global Awareness

Global Awareness entails the operational capability for all pertinent levels of command to know and understand the relevant global military situation on a common, consistent basis. From the Air Forces' perspective, Global Awareness consists of "awareness" at both a local and a global level.

Global Awareness is superior knowledge supported by superior information which enable operational dominance. The specific capabilities necessary to achieve Global Awareness are:

a. Consistent Battlespace Knowledge. The capabilities to elevate the level and speed of the warfighter's cognitive understanding of friendly, enemy, neutral, and geospatial situations, and to maintain consistency in that view across strategic, tactical and support forces.

b. Precision Information. The capabilities to develop and manage sufficient, and timely multi-modal operational information to assure an accurate, precise situational awareness and achieve Consistent Battlespace Knowledge.

c. Global Information Base. The capabilities to acquire, deconflict, fuse, store, maintain, support, and display world-wide operationally relevant data. Capabilities include in-time tasking and zooming, consistency, integrity and authentication.

The key role of Rome Laboratory will be research to provide better real-time information to the warfighter using existing data sources, by the creation of affordable new data sources, by streamlined data analysis, by reducing the footprint required to manage Global Awareness, and by extending the life of sensors in place and enhancing their performance.

The effective integration of Global Awareness within a true system-of-systems will provide the warfighter the tools required to successfully conduct the mission as depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Global Awareness

Dynamic Planning and Execution

Dynamic Planning and Execution describes the future operational capability to exploit superior, consistent knowledge of the battlespace in order to shape and control the pace and phasing of engagements through automated decision making. Dynamic

planning and execution extends to a total warfare planning process from readiness and deployment planning to shooter engagement and across the full spectrum of foreseeable military operations (Figure 2).

Dynamic Planning/Execution

Global Power

Figure 2. Dynamic Planning/Execution

The specific operational capability elements are:

a. Joint, Combined & Coalition Operations/Virtual Battlestaff. The capabilities needed to achieve dynamic synchronization of missions and resources from components and coalition forces.

b. Full Spectrum Dominance (Strategic and Tactical). "Capability-based" force level planning, across the full spectrum of possible military operations, to tailor forces to operations with minimized deployment footprint and logistics tail while achieving dominance.

c. Execution of Time Critical Missions/Real Time Sensor to Shooter Operations. The capabilities needed to enable target acquisition, battle management analysis, decision,

and resource assignment, and in-time engagement. These capabilities extend to a broad spectrum of time critical missions from time phased attack of fixed and moving targets to the use of hunter-controller-killer assets.

d. Predictive Planning & Preemption. The capabilities needed to be proactive in the planning process across echelons, missions, components, and coalition forces. These capabilities extend to integrating other than hard kill weapons, logistics and intelligence/surveillance/reconnaissance (IRS) management into the planning process, as well as planning to anticipate and avoid surprise.

The key role of the Laboratory will be to reduce planning/execution cycle time by (a) developing real-time assignment of assets to

missions, (b) accelerating generation and evaluation of options, (c) reducing and distributing the C4I footprint, and (d) enhancing joint and coalition planning & deployment of assets.

Seamless Communications/Connectivity

Figure 3. Seamless Communications/Connectivity

Seamless Communications and Connectivity

The ability to communicate, to move raw and processed information throughout a global communications grid (Figure 3), is fundamental to Command and Control. Inherent in this capability the idea of universal information availability across different transmission media with different characteristics. The specific operational capability elements are:

a. Universal transaction services. The ability to move information on demand from network to network or link to link without translation or conversion.

b. Full access to global communications grid. The ability of the infrastructure to provide over the horizon communication up to and including the cockpit, anywhere, anytime.

c. Self healing infrastructure. The infrastructure is flexible enough that modifying connectivity is a reconfiguration activity, rather than an engineering problem.

Seamless communication/connectivity consists of four primary functional capabilities, (a) distributed information

infrastructure, (b) universal transaction services, (c) assurance of services, and (d) global connection to aerospace forces (including shooters).

The key role of the Laboratory will be to enable global information exchange through (a) developing real-time system management, (b) establishing interconnect between dissimilar military/commercial networks, (c) developing counter-information warfare capability, (d) reducing deployed

communications footprint, and (e) integrating all airborne platforms (including shooter).

Core Competencies

Rome Laboratory C² development is supported by a set of technologies which span the realm of information gathering, processing, and presentation as depicted in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Core Competencies

Although each area has some commercial investment, the application to C² is particular to the service laboratories. To ensure that this remains the case, investment strategy includes constant review of the R&D portfolio of the Laboratory both from within, and outside. In aggregate, each of the core competencies support common particular R&D themes from shared attributes: (a) life cycle affordability, (b) rapid transition to the warfighter, and (c) a reduced C² footprint.

2. AIR FORCE C3I OPTO-ELECTRONIC FOCUS

Introduction

Current C² electronic systems are susceptible to electro-magnetic interference. Size constraints, speed and reliability also limit traditional electronic systems. Photonic-based systems, that process information in the form of light (photonics) signals, will provide major improvements in tactical and strategic C3I systems by providing small size, high performance, high capacity, survivable alternatives to electronic-based systems.

The goals of the Rome Laboratory photonics program are to develop high capacity/rapid access memory (one thousand trillion bits with nano second access), systems, high speed/ performance compact signal processors, wavelength division multiplexed

(WDM) communication systems, and integratable opto-electronic devices for C³I.

Optical interconnects, including high capacity I/O fiber and free-space board-to-board and on-chip links are a near term emphasis. Monolithic unidirectional waveguide semiconductor ring lasers have been recently developed. These low cost integratable devices feature low noise and large dynamic range for analog inter/intra chip optical interconnects. Another effort is evaluating electro-optical computing architectures in an existing model 3-D computing system. This will develop multi-function electro-optic interfaces and optical interconnect units to enhance the performance of a parallel processor system, and form the building blocks for future electro-optic computing architecture.

Significant advances are continuing in the development of vertical cavity surface emitting lasers (VCSELs) and modulators integrated with electronic logic, through both contractual and in-house efforts. Planes of smart pixel arrays interconnected via free space optics allow ultrahigh throughput digital signal processing or neural net computing to occur. Methods of obtaining high density interconnects with high throughput and low power devices are under development and are beginning to make technological strides in the commercial market.

An Integrated Optical Processor (IOP) program is designing the types of optically implemented hardware which will enhance near-term upgrades of DoD battlefield surveillance platforms. This program is focusing on integrating C³I functions (i.e., imagery, surveillance and ESM) with optical interconnect based processor designs, optical memory and hybrid analog/digital opto-electronic processors. Two parallel efforts in this arena are working with the requirements and system design integrators of current Airborne Warning and Control System (AWACS) and Joint Surveillance Target Attack Radar System (STARS) airborne platforms. A unique relationship is developing between Rome Laboratory, the

Air Force System Program Office, and the systems design contractor to provide the user with advanced capabilities well beyond the range of envisioned electronic digital processors.

The optical memory subthrust includes pre-prototype demonstrations of the two photon 3-dimensional terabit memory. The three dimensional optical memory (sugar cube) development has progressed to the point where the chemistry has been finalized for the Write Once Read Many times configuration. Writing architectures have been developed and tested for both orthogonal and pulse collision. Error correction and detection algorithms testing has begun with excellent results. A prototype reader has been fabricated to demonstrate feasibility.

WDM Communications

Rome Laboratory is currently developing/deploying wavelength division multiplexing (WDM) communication systems for use in DoD In-Theater (local area network) C³I systems. The first system to be discussed is a WDM fiber optic transmission system, deployed by NATO forces in Germany. This system multiplexes NTSC video, RGB video, audio, and network data onto a single fiber to provide multimedia communications between Command and Control shelters (See Figure 5). The use of this system reduces the number of required fibers from 60 to 18. The second system to be discussed is a WDM Asynchronous Transfer Mode (ATM) fiber optic transmission system, that will multiplex multiple ATM/OC-3 channels. This system, which is currently being developed, will be integrated with an Air Force Distributed Air Operations Center for test and demonstration in 1997 (See Figure 7).

Fiber optic communication technology is being developed with specific applications to broadband network backbones and high speed desktop multimedia communications for DoD C³I applications. The technology is based on a fiber optic WDM that simultaneously carries bi-directional FDDI, ATM/Taxi, ATM/OC-3, NTSC or RGB

video, and many other types of signals in a single pair of fibers. The technology can be used as a point-to-point network extender, or can be used in a ring-based add/drop network configuration for high-speed universal multiprotocol network access.

WDM is a fiber optic multiplexing technique that multiplexes (or demultiplexes) independent optical signals or different optical wavelengths from separate channels onto a single fiber (and vice versa), providing non-interfering passive combination and splitting of signals in the optical domain. This optical multiplexing technique eliminates the need for the synchronization, clocking, and buffering circuitry required in conventional electronic time division multiplexing (TDM) approaches. Thus, the support of multiple diverse data traffic types with different clocking requirements places no additional overhead in the WDM.

The WDM communication system (see Figure 6) consists of a set of two basic functional building blocks. One is a fiber optic WDM card; the other is a data-channel card. The WDM communication system is a chassis design with multiple slots. The WDM card occupies two slots, and different data-channel cards are used in the rest of the slots.

The WDM card consists of only fiber optic WDM components. Data signals from different data-channel cards in the chassis are delivered into the WDM card through a fiber optic adapter backplane at the rear of the WDM card. The output fiber of the WDM is then connected to a fiber optic connector in the front end of the WDM card to deliver all of the multiplexed data channels in a single transmission fiber. This is connected to a corresponding WDM communication system in a remote location. Similarly, in the demultiplexing operation, a fiber optic wavelength division demultiplexing component is used to demultiplex multiplexed data-channels from a second transmission fiber into separate fibers, which are then connected to the appropriate data-channel cards via backplane fiber optic adapters. The WDM card is passive, and does not require electrical power or grounding.

It should be noted that the WDM communication system design allows the application of other multiplexing techniques, such as TDM, in addition to the existing WDM technique. This flexibility may provide additional communication channels, which can be incorporated into each existing WDM wavelength channel, especially for the same data traffic type in the same data-channel cards. For example, a single data-channel card can be designed, based on the TDM technique, to accommodate eight (8) Ethernet data channels, four (4) ATM/OC-3 data channels, or four (4) digital audio/video data channels.

A data channel card that accepts multi-channel data signals from the front panel of the card. The front panel channel connectors can be either fiber, twisted pair, or coaxial cable. This card can multiplex (or demultiplex) these data channels (via the TDM technique) into a single fiber through the modulation of a laser source. These TDM data channel cards are then connected (using fiber optic backplane adapters) to the WDM card for further multiplexing/demultiplexing operations. Using this hybrid TDM/WDM design, we can integrate various data channel cards to provide application-specific interfaces, as required by the network system.

It should also be stressed that the system uses an optical backplane design instead of a conventional electrical backplane. This provides the capability for higher speed data communications. In the backplane of the system, only power, ground, and management lines are needed for the data-channel cards, as the data transmission between cards is delivered through fiber optic backplane adapters rather than printed circuit lines.

With this optical backplane design, the overall bandwidth of the system can be easily increased using more WDM channels. For example, if there is a total of 16 global WDM channels (i.e., 16-channel fiber optic WDM components), the system will have a maximum of 16 data-channel card slots (each slot accommodates a single data-channel card). Each data-channel card is equipped

with a light source with a unique wavelength.
If all of these cards are 4-channel digital

audio/video data channel cards (each with ~
1.2 Gb/sec bandwidth), then the overall
system bandwidth will be 19.2 Gb/s.

Figure 5. WDM Fiber Optic Transmission System

Figure 6. WDM ATM Fiber Optic Transmission System

In-Theater WDM ATM Link Demonstration

Figure 7. Distributed AOC WDM ATM Fiber Optic Transmission Demonstration

Semiconductor Ring Lasers

A major bottleneck in very high speed information acquisition and processing systems is the rate of data communications within the system. As data rates increase on electrical buses, so does the power required to send the data and problems of cross talk and noise become more severe. These problems can be eliminated by using photons, instead of electrons, to transfer data from one point to another within the system. However, major limitations of current photonics data transmission components include the lack of easily integrable lasers and the noise level in the transmitter. For high rate analog data transmission, the noise level of the transmitter is especially critical. There is therefore a great need for small, integrable, very low noise, efficient optical sources for transmitting data at microwave and millimeter wave rates over relatively short distances. [3]

A characteristic of most applications for short distance optical interconnects is the highly parallel nature of such interconnects which require many transmitters and receivers. One of the most significant problems is the conversion of electrical to optical signals in a way which is efficient and compatible with silicon chip technology in terms of manufacturability, cost per function, size, reliability, and power density.[3]

Since 1990, the invention and demonstration of a new class of semiconductor lasers has met all of these requirements. In addition, it will likely have extremely low relative intensity noise levels. These devices are monolithic guided-wave diode ring lasers or Waveguide Diode Ring Lasers (WDRL). Unique properties of these devices include the ability to operate as unidirectional traveling wave oscillators and hence promise extremely low noise and sensitivity to

reflections. These are the first ring lasers to be completely constructed in low-order dielectric waveguides. In addition, these devices are unique in that they allow laser resonant cavities of engineerable high Q to be constructed using a highly manufacturable technology: chemically assisted ion beam etching (CAIBE); these cavities can be placed anywhere and in any orientation on a wafer, and these are the only diode ring lasers to contain a simple, variable output coupling mechanism as an intrinsic part of the cavity.[3]

These laser geometries have the potential to produce small, low threshold, monolithically integrated devices which can be easily coupled to planar waveguides and which does not require special facet coatings for high reflectivity. The basic configuration is a planar, triangular-ring, single mode, rib waveguide. Since all reflections can be total internal ones, the optical cavity can be high-Q, allowing for very low threshold current operation. These unique properties of manufacturability, integrability, adjustable Q with planar cavity, built in output coupler, non-reciprocal operation, and ultra-low noise make this a unique class of devices which are important for future study.[3]

The major objective of the work reported here was to gain a more complete understanding of the physics of the operation of these devices from both a theoretical and experimental approach to determine the performance limits of such structures. The work proposed for this study included theoretical modeling, comparison of the models with experimental results on actual devices, the development of design tools for producing high-power and low noise ring lasers, and the development of the lowest possible noise, high-power, monolithic ring laser for analog communication applications. While most of the work was to be done using the GaAs based material system, the program was also to contain a component to develop materials technology to produce monolithic ring lasers at 1.3 micron wavelengths in InP substrates.[3]

Integrated C4I Optical Processor

The performance limits of conventional approaches to air and ground surveillance are now being stressed by the emergence of low-observable threats, sophisticated electronic countermeasures, increased target densities, and the complexity of engagement of the modern battlefield. A number of multi-spectral sensor fusion techniques and electronic counter-counter measures have been identified as a means to increase surveillance capabilities against these threats. Processing requirements of many of these schemes, however, remain prohibitive, outpacing the rate of advance of conventional electronics. Optical processing techniques offer one potential solution of this processing dilemma.

The Integrated C4I Optical Processor (IOP) is specifically designed to meet the processing requirements of a future multifunction airborne surveillance system. Gigabyte per second parallel optical interconnects provide for massive data transfer rates between sensor, memory and processor nodes of the IOP. The processor nodes are a hybrid design marrying digital electronic modules enhanced by optical waveguide interconnects optical switches and optical memory to achieve a highly interactive, rapidly reconfigurable fault tolerant system. The processor nodes, as envisioned, will be capable of delivering greater than one trillion operations per second throughput.

IOP Processing Requirements - The processor throughput, memory and I/O requirements are based on the sensor suite and postulated algorithms for the sensors, non-sensor functions (target imaging and identification), and sensor fusion and management (Figure 8). The majority of the algorithms are derived from ongoing work in Radar, IRST, ESM, Image Processing, Communications and Sensor Fusion systems as part of existing long-term algorithm development efforts.

The estimated raw throughput requirements for the IOP in the far-term (2005) for each functional area (Radar, Comm, Intell, etc.)

are categorized into four groups. Preprocessing for adaptive beamforming, digital I/Q, receiver equalization, etc., requires very high throughput deterministic processing with systolic data flow. Implementation requires dedicated, optimized, fixed function hardware.

Fixed function signal processing for pulse compression, clutter filtering, range Doppler filtering, etc., requires high throughput deterministic processing with regular data flow. Implementation can be by non-optimized, moderately low level programmable hardware.

Programmable signal processing for range/doppler centroiding, tile classification, etc., requires moderate throughput, some data dependency and variable data flow. Implementation can be achieved with high-order-language (HOL) programmable general purpose vector processors.

Data processing for deghosting, target tracking, sensor management, etc., is non-deterministic and requires low throughput with variable control/data flow. Implementation can be achieved with HOL programmable general purpose scalar processors.

Electronics Technology Forecast for the IOP - The electronics technology forecast was undertaken to compare these technology predictions to the system processing requirements derived earlier. Areas where electronic technology is not viable or not cost effective, and where optical technology may offer an effective alternative were identified. Five technologies which are critical to the IOP and are discussed further are: 1) Analog to Digital Conversion, 2) Fixed Function Signal Processing, 3) Programmable Signal Processing, 4) Data Processing, and 5) Data Communications.

Figure 8. C³I Surveillance Multifunction Airborne Surveillance System Approach

In many cases, the sampling rate achievable by the A/D converter drives all subsequent signal processing requirements. During 1991, a 240 MHz, 8 bit ECL A/D converter was developed and demonstrated for a wideband (240 MHz) receiver. This sampling rate is sufficient to allow digital I/Q formation and digital channel-to-channel equalization. These digital approaches will be required to meet the low-observability and ECCM performance requirements of the IOP.

The Digital IQ/Receiver Equalization board developed at Westinghouse [2] is a state-of-the-art fixed function signal processor. The design is fully cascadeable, and was demonstrated in a 16 channel phased array receiver system. The GaAs version of the design is predicted to run at ~250MHz and deliver 30 BOPS.

The Westinghouse Systolic Vector Processor (SVP) provides for a state-of-the-art programmable signal processor. The SVP is based upon a fully programmable DSP microprocessor, the Complex Arithmetic Unit (CAU). The 0.75 micron BiCMOS version of the CAU could potentially operate at 50MHz and deliver 300 MOPS.

The proposed data processor is a configurable multiprocessor. The current system delivers 70 MIPS, 16 MBytes of RAM and four 160 Mbit/sec links in 4 square inches.

The Westinghouse Optical Data Link for Data Communication provides sustained data rates of 1 Gbit/sec via a single fiber cable. The design implements a full-duplex data link (2 Gigabits/sec aggregate bandwidth) and autonomously performs all clock recovery, synchronization, encoding/decoding and error detection and correction functions.

Optical Technology Forecast for the IOP - The optical technology forecast concentrated on optics technology which: 1) addresses a requirement that strongly stresses electronic technology, or 2) serves as an enabling technology that provides new or increased capabilities, or 3) provides comparable

performance while offering significant reduced size, weight and/or power. Four optical technologies considered for inclusion in the IOP design and discussed further are acousto-optics, optical numerical processing, optical interconnects and optical memories.

Acousto-optics for the IOP - The acousto-optic (AO) correlator was examined as a means to correlate an unknown vector against a library of stored templates. This function occurs repeatedly throughout the IOP, including the stressing applications of target classification/recognition, emitter identification, and target tracking (particularly in a multiple hypothesis fusion tracker, where the number of required correlations grows factorially with target density). This latter application is the subject of a critical technology demonstration.

The following comparative analysis was made between an AO correlator and a digital electronic processor. The analysis assumed that a 1024 bit vector (organized into 128 eight bit fields) is to be correlated against 1024 entries in a presorted library. The 128 fields might, for example, represent successive samples from a high resolution range radar return. Ten snapshots of the return, taken in rapid succession are each correlated against the library. The ten results from each of the 1024 correlations are summed, with the entry resulting in the largest total declared as the identity of the unknown vector.

The AO correlator with an assumed bragg cell bandwidth of 100 MHz and a detector readout rate of 10 MHz would require a total processing time described by the calculation:

$$(10\text{trials/id}) \cdot (1024\text{bits/trial}) \cdot (10\text{ nsec/bit}) + (1024\text{ detectors}) \cdot (100\text{ nsec/detector}) = 205\text{ usec.}$$

The thresholding and comparisons required to identify the largest detector output may be performed by very simple electronic post-processing. This results in a maximum identification rate of 5000 id's/sec at an estimated power of 25 Watts.

The digital electronic solution commonly used to perform correlation is the computation of the arithmetic dot product of the unknown vector and each entry in the library. Each dot product would require 128 multiplies and 127 adds, for a total of 255 operations. Performing the dot product on all 1024 library entries would require 64,512 operations. Repeating this procedure for all 10 snapshots yields 645,120 operations. Integrating the 10 sets of results requires 9 adds * 1024 entries = 9216 ops. The total operation count for the digital implementation is thus, 654,336. To match the identical correlation time of 205 usec achieved by the AO correlator requires 654336 ops/205 usec = 3.2 BOPS.

Dedicated digital hardware comparable to the AO correlator in throughput and size would require 75 Watts or three times the power of the AO correlator. General purpose data processors with comparable throughput would consume 7500 Watts. The AO correlator therefore, serves as an excellent co-processor for the purpose of fused target tracking.

Optical Numerical Processing for the IOP - Optical Numerical Processing, specifically the implementation of a simple high-speed multiply-accumulator (MAC), is crucial since well over 95% of all operations performed by the IOP can be reduced to this rudimentary operation. The following analysis examines Residue Number System (RNS) implementations which require at least 28 bits of dynamic range. This is typical for matrix operations employed in adaptive beam forming.

The optical RNS processor developed by Westinghouse employs 5 modular RNS MACs providing 179 db (> 29 bits) of dynamic range. This implementation uses discrete component look-up tables, occupies 1600 in², consumes approximately 500 Watts and operates at 25 to 50 MHz.

Near-term electronic estimates, using a binary number system for MAC, would provide for a maximum operating frequency of 6.95 nsec or ~100 MHz. The electronic

RNS implementation, using factored look-up tables, would result in a maximum RNS operating frequency of 2.7 nsec or ~350 MHz. Both electronic implementations could easily be packaged into a single integrated circuit, requiring a total surface area of approximately 1.25 in² and dissipating 2 to 3 Watts. Therefore, optically-implemented RNS appears to have no obvious advantage in the near term.

Far-term estimates of an optical implementation assumed a monolithic surface emitting laser diode array, with gates positioned on 10 mil x 10 mil centers, dissipating 1.5 mW/gate. Photodiodes would occupy 100 mils² and dissipate 5 mW. The estimated operating frequency would be ~10 GHz. These estimates provide for an implementation which is approximately 12 in², dissipates 7.5 Watts and has a throughput of 20 BOPS.

Far-term electronic estimates show the maximum binary operating frequency of ~400 MHz, and a maximum RNS frequency of ~1.2 GHz. Therefore the far-term estimates show an 8:1 speed advantage of optical RNS versus an electronic RNS implementation, and a 25:1 speed advantage over binary electronics.

Optical Interconnects for the IOP - Optical Interconnects play a significant role in meeting the throughput requirements of a future multi-function airborne surveillance system. Optical interconnects are required for both distributed (sensor to processor, node to node), and localized (backplane level) interconnects.

Performance estimates for a proposed distributed electrical interconnect scheme were derived by means of a transmission line analysis. The theoretical upper limit for data transmission over a 50' twisted pair line was ~0.225 Gbits/sec.

Performance estimates for distributed optical interconnect schemes were derived by engineers from the photonics laboratory at Honeywell's Systems and Research Center.[2] Due to the overhead in power and

physical size involved in converting from electrical to optical signals, maximum tolerable use of multiplexing is made. Electronic multiplexing is used to the point where the serial data rate reaches the maximum speed permitted by the circuit technology.

Beyond this point optical multiplexing techniques such as TDM or WDM are required. In the near term, electronic multiplexing schemes can be expected to deliver 5 to 6 GHz/sec serialized data rates. Far-term electronic multiplexing schemes may be limited to serialized data rates of 20 GHz, while optical TDM (preferred over WDM due to issues of ensuring component stability) may provide for data rates in excess of 100 GHz.

Performance estimates for localized backplane level electronic interconnects were based on a circuit similar to the emerging IEEE 896.2 (FutureBus+) interconnect standard. Transmission line analysis showed a maximum near-term data transfer rate of $1/18.4 \text{ nsec} = 54 \text{ MHz}$. For a 32-bit-wide bus, this corresponds to a transfer bandwidth of 1.7 Gbits/sec. For far-term estimates, a theoretical upper limit can be derived resulting in a maximum clock rate of 135 MHz, or 4.3 Gbits/sec. More realistic long term estimates would be ~100 MHz, as predicted by the IEEE 896.2 standard.

The performance estimates for both serial and parallel localized optical interconnects were made assuming a variety of technology implementations. For data rates below ~50 Mbits/sec per data line it was determined that there is little power or size benefit from employing optics, and parallel electrical buses remain competitive. Between 50 and 100 Mbits/sec per data line optics begins to offer both size and power advantages. At ~100 Mbits/sec per data line, synchronous electrical interconnects are poorly suited and optical interconnects become the enabling technology. The lowest power dissipation in the near term is likely to be realized using CHFET GaAs electronics in conjunction with high speed optical components.

Optical Memories for the IOP - The IOP design contains a wide variety of memory configurations and requirements. The most stressing applications can be divided into four distinct categories. Scratchpad memory, typified by the corner-turn memories of the radar node, is characterized by high-speed, short-term storage of real-time data (on the order of 10's of milliseconds).

Archival memory, typified by the scan-to-scan frame buffer of the Infra Red Search and Track (IRST) node, is characterized by moderate-speed, intermediate storage of real-time data (on the order of 5-10 seconds).

Database memory, typified by the associative memory of the Non Cooperating Target Identification (NCTI) node, is a write once, read many (WORM) memory, with large size, and non-real-time write and real-time read requirements.

Recording memory, typified by the signal recording memory of the ESM node, is characterized by very large size (on the order of gigabytes) with non-real-time read/write requirements.

The state-of-art assessment of optical memories concluded that the optical "jukebox" developed by Rome Laboratory (RL) was ready for insertion into the IOP. The Optical Associative Memory being developed by RL is also a potential candidate for optical memory insertion. Optical WORMs are commercially available.

3-D MEMORIES

Conventional memory technologies have improved dramatically over the past decade. However, each with their projected increase in capacity, data rate access time, these memory devices cannot meet the demands of many future high performance digital applications, especially fast image storage and retrieval including graphics, multi-media and video on demand. Optical 3-D memories have emerged as potential candidates to overcome the limitations of these current memories.

Rome Laboratory recently completed a three year study on the feasibility of using two-photon interactions to implement bit oriented 3-D memories.[4] The study was conducted by Call/Recall Corporation, and its sub-contractors UCI, UCSD, and the University of Alabama, Huntsville.

The goal of the research was 1) to develop materials which will be capable of storing information in a 3-D bit oriented format by two-photon interaction and be suitable for the reading of the stored information, 2) to design system architectures and to specify the required peripheral devices needed and, 3) to show the feasibility of a two-photon 3-D memory system.

All of the goals were archived. Means were devised for storing information in 3-D by two-photon virtual absorption. The molecular system designed exhibits two distinct photon-induced forms which are used, as the zero and one, for information storing and retrieving. Writing is achieved by two simultaneous absorption of two photons, one at 532 nm and the other at 1064 nm and the reading is achieved by the detection of the fluorescence emitted, by the write molecules only, after excitation with two 1064 nm photons or by one 532 nm photon. Many types of materials were investigated for their suitability for this process and at least two (one for read-write-erase system and the other for read only systems) have shown promising results.

Several system architectures have been devised and studied based on this physical principal and materials. These are orthogonally addressed, pulse collision addressed and micro-channel addressed architectures. For the orthogonally addressed architecture, the required peripheral devices were determined, their commercial availability and suitability investigated or the means of implementing these devices pursued. Special emphasis has been put towards the development of fast dynamic focusing lenses which are critical for this architecture. Based on this peripheral device investigation and developed materials, memory performance parameters such as capacity, data transfer rates and access times

have been estimated for variations of this architecture. The other two architectures were only studied in terms of their potential and are presently being investigated in a follow on program.

To demonstrate the feasibility of a two-photon absorption based 3-D memory system, several patterns were written inside the volume of a 3-D cube and then read out. The experiment was also used to characterize the material-device interface parameters of two-photon memories such as uniformity, retention time, fatigue and erasure dynamics. The automatization of this system and its interfacing to a digital computer is being carried out in a new program.

Additional Accomplishments and Future Directions

In addition to the previously described accomplishments, the Rome Laboratory Photonics Program had numerous additional accomplishments in optoelectronics technology development for C3I applications in 1995-1996. A summary of these accomplishments is as follows:

demonstration of a high dynamic range millimeterwave interconnect system.

first room temperature operation of InP vertical cavity surface emitting laser (VCSEL) at 1.55 micrometers.

demonstration of holographic image demultiplexing with up to 16,000 separate channels.

demonstration of a traveling wave photodetector with bandwidth efficiency product of 76 Ghz.

demonstration of high resolution/low loss true time delay at arbitrary radio frequency carrier.

successful field demonstration of an optical 2-18 Ghz antenna remoting system.

demonstration of a high optical power handling photodetector (20mW at 20 Ghz).

development of a secure optical personnel-entry biometric identification system based on phase-only optical correlation.

demonstration of high-performance metal semiconductor metal photo-detectors on indium gallium arsenide using substrate removal and backside illumination.

design of a unipolar silicon/zinc selenide quantum-well intersubband laser for use as an integrated optical source.

demonstration of multiplexing up to 40 color bands in an IR multispectral imaging system for spectral feature extraction.

development of the first bismuth silicate crystal with controlled photorefractive characteristics for optical processing applications using a unique hydrothermal growth technique.

development of the first detailed model of optical two-wave mixing gain in semi-insulating indium phosphide.

invention of a new method for measuring thickness and composition of thin semiconductor films to within 0.5% across the wafer.

The program also successfully delivered and integrated a 120 Gigabyte erasable, deployable Optical Disk Jukebox to Head Quarters Air Force Special Operations Command (HQ AFSOC) used for mission planning.

In 1997, the Rome Laboratory photonics program will begin the development for an optically controlled phased array Advanced Technology Demonstration (ATD) aimed at EHF airborne and spaceborne applications. The C4I optical processor ATD brassboard will be demonstrated. This processor will emphasize the utilization of optical interconnects and rapid access optical memory for near real-time interactive processing of sensor (active/passive), intelligence and imaging systems. Rome Lab will initiate a comprehensive RF signal distribution system ATD for secure remoting

of all radio frequencies up to 100 Ghz. Directly-modulated 25 Ghz lasers for analog fiber optic communications at 1.3 um wavelength will be fully packaged. This laser diode is a strained multiquantum-well device engineered for high-efficiency and low-cost.

In 1998, the program will complete development of a three-dimensional write once read many times (WORM) optical memory system ATD. A high capacity Terabyte Erasable Optical Disk Jukebox ATD will be integrated at the 480thIG, and Air Combat Command for Air Force Intelligence Network (AFINTNET) applications. An optically controlled phased array for airborne application at SHF, specifically the Defense Satellite Communications System (DSCS) will be demonstrated. The application of epitaxial transfer integration (ETI) to develop functional hybrid III-V optoelectronic integrated circuits on ceramic, organic and semiconductor substrates. Ultra high-fluence and ultra low-fluence optical detectors using bandgap engineered structures with advanced surface passivation technology at 1.3 - 1.5 um will be demonstrated. High performance silicon/indium gallium arsenide separate absorption and multiplication avalanche photodiodes using semiconductor fusion technology will be demonstrated.

In 1999, an erasable 3-D memory system will be demonstrated. An integrated infrared optical processor that can be resolved into color imagery will be demonstrated. High-speed vertical cavity surface-emitting lasers for room temperature, continuous wave operation at 1.3 - 1.5 um wavelength will be packaged

3. CONCLUSIONS

Rome Laboratory, as the lead Air Force Laboratory for C³I technology, supports a set of technologies which span the realm of information gathering, processing, and presentation. These technologies will provide the Air Force with capabilities to achieve Global Awareness, Dynamic Planning and Execution, and Seamless Global Communications.

Photonic (Opto-Electronic) technology developments will provide major improvements in AF tactical and strategic C³I systems by providing small size, high performance, high capacity, low power alternatives to electronic-based systems.

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Biography

Robert Kaminski received MS degrees from Syracuse University (Computer Science 89, Computer Engineering 94). He is a computer engineer at Rome Laboratory, Command, Control & Communications Directorate Griffiss AFB, New York. His research interests include network management and optical switching for communication networks. He is a member of SPIE, OSA, and IEEE.